

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF PERSONAL INCOME TAX IN THE FORMATION OF THE BUDGET OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

The article presents the results of the analysis of the dynamics of the receipt of personal income tax in the consolidated budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter RUz), shows the importance of the tax as the most stable source of tax revenues of the regional budget, and identifies the main factors influencing tax collection.

Keywords: consolidated budget, tax, tax revenues, fiscal function, income, personal income tax

Introduction

In the context of rapid development of society, it is necessary to constantly form sustainable resources to meet the needs of society and the state at various stages of development. In this case, there is a need to analyze the level of efficiency of sources of formation of state budget revenues. Article 51 of the Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the following sources of revenue of the republican budget[1]: 1) in accordance with established standards:

- income tax;
- personal income tax;
- excise tax;
- subsoil use tax (except for subsoil use tax on construction materials);
- 2) customs duties;
- 3) value added tax;
- 4) other income.

In Uzbekistan, personal income tax plays a pivotal role in shaping the national budget, contributing significantly to public services and infrastructure development. The relevance of the problems under study is determined by the fact that one of the most important sources of income for the national budget of Uzbekistan is the personal income tax (hereinafter referred to as PIT). The peculiarity of PIT is that it is a generally established tax, i.e., it is in effect throughout the entire territory of Uzbekistan, which allows for strengthening the budget's revenue base, due to the fact that, firstly,

its payers are almost the entire working-age population of the country; secondly, it is easier for tax authorities to control it than other taxes, and it is more difficult for dishonest taxpayers to evade paying it; thirdly, the volume of tax revenues is directly affected by the expansion of its taxable base - an increase in the wages of the population [2].

Methodology.

The article used the following methods and techniques of scientific research: theoretical methods of cognition, a systematic approach to the theoretical presentation of income tax, analysis and synthesis as methods of summarizing the results, comparison and measurement, the induction method for summarizing the results of the study of income tax revenues to the budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In our study, we tried to deeply study the problem using comparative and statistical analysis of the areas of analytical analysis. Strategic directions are established that lead to the solution of the problem. As an object of research, the statistical indicators of tax revenues to the budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied.

Results.

The importance of the personal income tax in the state financial system can be assessed by analyzing two main indicators: 1. The share of this tax in the total and tax revenues of the budget; 2. The share of the tax in the country's GDP.

Table 1

The share of personal income tax in the budgets of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period from 2020 to 2023.¹

Years	Budget revenues, total (billion soums)	Tax revenues of the budget (billion soums)	PIT (billion soums)	Share of personal income tax in total budget revenues, %	Share of personal income tax in budget tax revenues, %
2020	132 938,1	109 338,5	15 140,80	11,40	13,8
2021	164 799,4	133 492,3	18 917,70	11,40	14,2
2022	201 863,7	154 004,4	24 284,50	12,00	15,7
2023	231 721,3	174 902,8	29 917,40	12,91	17,1

The dynamics of the share of personal income tax in the total and tax revenues of the consolidated budget

of the country has a growth trend (Table 1). In the period under study, it fluctuated from 13.8% to 17.1% of

¹ [Compiled by the author based on the openbudget.uz database].

tax revenues and did not exceed 1/8 of the total budget revenues.

It should be noted that the share of personal income tax in the total volume of tax revenues in the budgets of most developed countries is significantly higher. Thus, an analysis of foreign taxation showed that, for example, in Great Britain, the share of income tax in total tax revenues is 33-34%; in Germany 27-

28%, in the USA 45-47%, and in Sweden or Denmark it exceeds 50% [3].

This circumstance is mainly due to the rather low level of income of the majority of the population in Uzbekistan, low tax discipline of taxpayers, as well as the low level of tax rates for high incomes of individuals - 12% regardless of the amount of income received. In developed countries, the tax rate fluctuates from 55 to 79% (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Countries with the highest personal income tax rates 2021-2023.²

For comparison, the maximum income tax rate (for the highest incomes of citizens) is: in Belgium - 79.5%, in Finland - 66.75%, in Portugal - 64%, in Great Britain - 63.25%, in Switzerland - 57%, in Japan - 55% [4].

A significant indicator of the importance of personal income tax in the financial security of the country is also its share in GDP in (Table 2).

Table 2
Dynamics of the share of personal income tax in the GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period from 2020 to 2023.³

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023
GDP, billion soums	605 514,90	738 425,20	896 617,90	1 066 569,00
Personal income tax, billion soums	15 140,80	18 917,70	24 284,50	29 917,40
Share of personal income tax in GDP, %	2,50	2,56	2,71	2,81

The table above shows that income tax makes up a significant part of GDP year after year. In particular, in 2020, the share of income tax in GDP was 2.50%,

and by 2023 this figure reached 2.81%. It is interesting to compare the dynamics of GDP growth rates and personal income tax revenues to the budget (Fig. 2).

² [Compiled by the author based on the worldpopulationreview.com database. Source: Highest Taxed Countries 2024 (<https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/highest-taxed-countries>)]

³ [Compiled by the author based on the openbudget.uz database].

Fig. 2. Dynamics of growth rates of tax revenues and GDP.⁴

It shows a certain time lag in the dynamics of the rate of change of personal income tax compared to the same indicator of the gross product. At the same time, during periods of economic growth, the fiscal function of the tax is weakened, and during periods of decline, it is strengthened. Thus, the proportional income taxation

of individuals in force in the Republic of Uzbekistan does not allow using personal income tax as an automatic regulator when implementing countercyclical state policy. This significantly distinguishes the income taxation of Uzbekistan and economically developed countries (Tab. 3).

Table 3

The structure of tax revenues of the regional budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2022.⁵

Indicators	2020		2021		2022		2023	
	billion soum	%						
Profits tax	28 712,20	26	38 363,30	28	37 649,90	24	40 778,90	23
Value Added Tax	31 177,40	28	38 439	28	52 189,40	33	57 885,30	33
Subsoil use tax	16 417,10	15	15 811,90	11	13 887,40	9	15 300,30	8
Personal Income Tax	15 140,80	13	18 917,70	14	24 284,50	15	29 917,40	17
Other tax revenues	17 891,00	16	21 960,40	16	25 993,20	16	31 020,90	17

Personal income tax ranks third in terms of revenues to the regional budget. At the same time, over the analyzed period, there has been an increase in the share of this tax and by the end of 2023 it was 17.7% (the share of the first largest tax - corporate income tax, on the contrary, decreased over this period and by the end of 2023 it was 23.5%). The main reason for this is the stability and high collection rate of personal income tax to the regional budget. That is, it can be argued that it is the most significant and stable tax source of revenue for the regional budget.

The main tax revenues are formed from income taxed at a rate of 12%, the source of which are tax agent organizations. The above allows us to make an obvious conclusion that comprehensive support by regional and local authorities of small and medium-sized enterprises will help maintain a stable level of revenue receipts to the relevant budget, and will also contribute to increasing employment and, consequently, the socio-political stability of the region.

Conclusion

In Uzbekistan, the personal income tax (PIT) is levied on the income of individuals received as a result of labor activity, as well as from the sale of property, gifts and other sources. This tax plays an important role in the formation of the budget of Uzbekistan, providing a significant inflow of funds to the state treasury.

Scientists, based on their research, recommended increasing the role of the stimulating nature of the PIT [5]. We also believe that it is necessary to improve the PIT taxation system. The current taxation procedure does not observe the stimulating role of the tax.

In addition, the PIT performs a stimulating function. Thanks to this tax, the state can regulate the level of income of citizens, prevent their excessive increase, and stimulate the development of certain sectors of the economy or regions. This allows the state to maintain social stability and economic growth.

⁴ [Compiled by the author based on the openbudget.uz database].

⁵ [Compiled by the author based on the openbudget.uz database.]

PIT also performs a distribution function. With its help, the state redistributes part of the income of citizens in favor of needy segments of the population, pensioners, disabled people and other categories of citizens in need of social support.

Therefore, based on the experience of developed countries, we believe that it is necessary to improve the system of taxation of individuals and pay more attention to the administration of income tax as a stable source of income for the state budget.

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